

First record of the theridiid spider *Rhomphaea affinis* Lessert, 1936 from South Africa (Arachnida: Theridiidae)

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ABSTRACT: The Mozambican tailed comb-foot spider, *Rhomphaea affinis* Lessert, 1936, was described from Mozambique and was only known from the type locality. This spider was recorded for the first time from South Africa during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA). The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Rhomphaea* L. Koch, 1872 is represented by 37 species, and has a wide distribution (World Spider Catalog, 2022). *Rhomphaea* species are still poorly documented in South Africa and only *R. nasicus* (Simon, 1873) was listed in the first Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). Members of *Rhomphaea* differ from other argyrodines by the following putative synapomorphies (Levi & Levi, 1962):

- Abdomen elongate, usually boomerang shaped.
- Posterior tip of abdomen with modified sturdy setae.
- Ocular projection elongate.
- Male palp with embolus tip elongate and strongly ridged basally and palp tibia elongate, but not scoop shaped.
- Egg sac rhomboid shaped (Exline & Levi, 1962).
- Possibly unique prey capture strategy (Whitehouse, 1987; Exline & Levi, 1962).

Rhomphaea affinis Lessert, 1936 was recorded for the first time from South Africa during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and the first photographs of the species were taken by the second author. Little is still known about them and the aim of this paper is to provide information on their morphology based on live specimens, behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

METHODS

The specimens examined are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. The photographs were taken by the second author and form part of the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Rhomphaea affinis Lessert, 1936

Rhomphaea affinis Lessert, 1936: 236, f. 31–32 (Df); Agnarsson, 2004: 479.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size TL: 5–6 mm. Body elongate (Figs 1–2). Carapace as wide as long; bulging towards posterior edge (Fig. 8); fawn with blackish-brown marginal band and two longitudinal lines; blackish-brown parallels from the anterior median eyes reaching the end of the chelicerae. Anterior eyes seen from above are recurved; the medians a little larger than the lateral, very close to the latter. Clypeus slanting, long; chelicerae extend forwards (Fig. 8). Abdomen fawn and decorated with silver spots; elongate, extending past the spinnerets, usually boomerang shape; caudal extremity posterior

Figs 1–2. *Rhomphaea affinis* female in web from Winterton. Photos: Johan van Zyl.

prolonged in small vermiform curved, modified sturdy seta (Figs 4–6). Legs long and slender; femora fawn and decorated with a brown subapical band and dark stripes (Fig. 8). Epigyne a wide atrium with two dark triangular markings on both sides (Fig. 7). Male unknown.

Figs 3–8. *Rhomphaea affinis*: 3. Line drawing of abdomen of female lateral view. 4–6. Close-up of the caudal tip of abdomen showing the curved sturdy seta. 7. Epigyne. 8. Lateral view of the carapace. Credits: 3–4 & 7 after Lessert (1936). 5 & 8. Johan van Zyl. 6. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Mozambique (Bas Mouira, Nhampalamassa) and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Free State: Sandveld Nature Reserve Camp (-27.40, 25.41). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57); Kosi Bay Coastal Forest (-26.57, 32.49); Winterton (-28.81, 29.53).

Map showing distribution in South Africa

BEHAVIOUR

Little is still known about the behaviour of *Rhomphaea* species. These tiny, cryptic spiders are rare and difficult to spot in grasses and bushes and their body shape helps to camouflage them. Research also showed that the spiders with their worm-like abdomens are flexible and are able to change shape. When the abdomen is for example held out long and straight, the spiders look like sticks and blend in with the vegetation they rest on. Exline and Levi (1962) were the first to observe *Rhomphaea* species making their own webs.

In Australia, a *Rhomphaea* sp. was observed by Whitehouse (1987) hanging in the middle of a horizontal web (Fig. 9). The body of the spiders spanned the gap as it rested on the web, but it did not tense the lines or sag them as other spiders do with similar reduced webs. They only came out at night. During the day they rested by hanging about 5 mm below a branch. The *Rhomphaea* sp. by using aggressive mimicry then lures other spiders to then throw a sticky triangular net over the prey (Fig. 10).

In a photograph of *R. affinis* taken in Winterton, a female can be seen hanging in a web with legs II, III, and IV grabbing silk threads (Fig. 11) filling a gap. Unfortunately no prey was near to see whether she will produce a sticky triangle web.

Fig. 9. Web of a *Rhomphaea* sp. located in a bush in Australia. The spider is hanging in the middle of the horizontal thread (After Whitehouse, 1987).

Fig. 10. *Rhomphaea* sp. producing a triangle net just prior to catching prey (After Whitehead, 1987).

Figures 11. *Rhomphaea affinis* female found at night hanging in a sparse web in Winterton. Photo: Johan van Zyl.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

The species is probably under-sampled and might be present in more African countries. There are presently no significant threats to this species but more sampling is needed to collect the male. In South Africa it is protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve, Ithala Nature Reserve, Sandveld Nature Reserve, and Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve.

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